

Possibility of Two New Bosons

By Deep Jyoti Dutta*

* Division of Nuclear Physics (DNP), American Physical Society, One Physics Ellipse, College Park, Maryland, United States of America

In this note the possible existence of two new bosons is highly speculated. One scalar charged boson and one fractional charged gauge boson like w boson. Both particles are predicted as elementary.

Standard model of particle physics holds brilliant till date but solutions of many problems are left unanswered. No proper explanation is suggested yet. In this note we will use abstract mathematics only and only to predict two fundamental bosons one scalar and the vector boson. In standard model there are six leptons and six quarks and all are of spin $\frac{1}{2}$ means they are fermions and must obey exclusion principle. Consider six components given by

$$\nabla\psi = \begin{pmatrix} Q_1 & Q_2 & Q_3 \\ Q_6 & Q_5 & Q_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \phi_1 & \phi_2 & \phi_3 \\ \phi_6 & \phi_5 & \phi_4 \end{pmatrix}$$

And simply introducing rules as rule 1 and rule 2

$$G_0 = (\phi_3 + \phi_6) + (\phi_1 + \phi_4) + (-\phi_2 - \phi_5) \text{ above symbolized by Q RULE 1}$$

$$G_1 = (\phi_3 - \phi_6) + (\phi_1 + \phi_4) + (-\phi_2 - \phi_5) \text{ RULE 2}$$

W boson has a charge +1 and spin has 1 so clearly. And we have fundamental bosons of spin range 1 and 0 (the only Higgs boson) and a charge range 0 and +1 such that

For spin

$$\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi_3 = \phi_4 = \phi_5 = \phi_6 \neq 0$$

$$\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi_3 = \phi_4 = \phi_5 = \phi_6 > 0$$

And

$$\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi_3 = \phi_4 = \phi_5 = \phi_6 < 1$$

Similarly for charge

$$\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi_3 = \phi_4 = \phi_5 = \phi_6 \neq 0$$

$$\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi_3 = \phi_4 = \phi_5 = \phi_6 > 0$$

And

$$\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi_3 = \phi_4 = \phi_5 = \phi_6 < 1$$

Allowing the choice to be fit in $\nabla\psi$

$$\phi_1 = q_+, \phi_2 = q_-$$

Where q are quarks of respective charges (+2/3) and (-1/3).

$$\phi_1 = \phi_3 = \phi_5 = q_+$$

$$\phi_2 = \phi_4 = \phi_6 = q_-$$

So that it forms

$$\nabla\psi = \begin{pmatrix} q_+ & q_- & q_+ \\ q_- & q_+ & q_- \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} u & d & c \\ b & t & s \end{pmatrix}$$

The choice is based on following pattern

ϕ_1 and ϕ_2 are first generation quarks, ϕ_3 and ϕ_4 are second generation quarks and

ϕ_5 and ϕ_6 are third generation quarks

Considering with spin $J = 1/2$ choices by taking

$$\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi_3 = \phi_4 = \phi_5 = \phi_6 = J$$

Or

$$u = d = c = s = t = b = J$$

$$\nabla\psi = \begin{pmatrix} u & d & c \\ b & t & s \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} J & J & J \\ J & J & J \end{pmatrix}$$

Using rule 1 for spin use and charge use independently

From calculation one obtains a particle of spin 1 and a charge of +1/3

So First achievement we get a particle say P_B

$$spin = 1$$

$$charge = +\frac{1}{3}$$

Simply we have the charge P_B

$$Q_{P_B} = (Q_{w^+} - q^+) = 1 - \frac{2}{3} = \frac{1}{3}$$

Where Q_{w^+} is the charge of w^+ boson = +1.

For second case we have rule 2 for spin use and charge use independently

From same choices above and calculating from rule 2 for spin and charge (independently) one obtains second particle say P_A whose charge and spin is

$$spin = 0$$

$$charge = +1$$

From above calculations we obtains two bosons one fractional charged vector boson and the other is integer charged scalar boson

The decay of the above predicted two particles are predicted

It clearly seems that both particles' mass is heavier than Higgs boson and our choice w boson

$$M_H < M_{P_B} \text{ (experiments required)}$$

$$M_W < M_{P_B} \text{ (experiments required)}$$

$$M_H < M_{P_A} \text{ (experiments required)}$$

$$M_W < M_{P_A} \text{ (experiments required)}$$

The decay structure for these proposed particles seems very complex right now. This paper offers very preliminary predictions which we propose to my experimenter friends to detect such candidate in particle accelerators.